

The Poetry “Raşit Bey”; (in memory of Judge (Hâkim) “Raşit Elmas”)

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Abstract

IN MEMORY OF JUDGE (HÂKİM) “RAŞİT ELMAS”

This paper composes a “Poem” completely written by “Âşık Veysel ŞATIROĞLU”, who was Turkish popular folk literature poet – folk music singer – songwriter, saz (bağlama) instrument virtuoso player and Great Poet, dated 30/12/1972 at Sivrialan Village of Şarkışla, Sivas, Türkiye. “Âşık Veysel” had written this poetry for “Raşit ELMAS” who was a “Judge” at Şarkışla at the time of the poem was written. The name (the title) of the poetry is “Raşit Bey”, it is in Turkish and it contains 4 stanzas. This poetry is also a valuable art piece of Turkish Folk Literature.

As a brief biography; “Raşit ELMAS” was born in Kastamonu, Türkiye on June 25, 1940. He has graduated from Faculty of Law at İstanbul University and then completed his military service as a Lieutenant - Reserved Officer. Raşit ELMAS was a “Judge” and he dispensed justice in several cities of Türkiye during long years. After being a “Retired Judge”, he has worked as a “Lawyer”, as well. He passed away and bid farewell to the life on January 11, 2023 at Akhisar, Türkiye. His photograph is at the below section of the poem.

When “Raşit ELMAS” was a “Judge” at Şarkışla, he and “Âşık Veysel” had a valuable relationship-friendship and he had respect for the Great Poet. The Poem named as “Raşit Bey” which is published on this paper was written by “Âşık Veysel ŞATIROĞLU” and dedicated to “Raşit ELMAS” by “Âşık Veysel” on 30/12/1972 at Sivrialan Village of Şarkışla, Sivas, Türkiye.

After “Raşit ELMAS” has passed away, his family members who are; his wife “Tuna ELMAS” (who is a Lawyer), his son “Emin Taner ELMAS” (who is an academician and the author of this manuscript) and his daughter “Esra ELMAS” (who is an Archaeologist and also an English Teacher) decided to publish this “Original Poetry Literature” entitled as “Raşit Bey” in memory of him.

RAŞİT BEY

Raşit Bey sen Hâkimsin,
Suyu süttten ayırırsın,
Karşına çıkan haksıza
Kanun hükmün duyurursun.

Ayrılmazsın adaletten,
Kaçınırsın nedametten,
Raşit Bey selametten
Doğru yollarda yürürsün.

Oturduğun makam yüce,
Çalışırsın gündüz gece,
Yetişmek için amaca
Kanunlara başvurursun.

Hâkimlerde olmaz hile,
Veysel Âşık tatlı dile,
Hâkimler benzer bülbüle
Gülü hardan ayırırsın.

Photograph: Judge (Hâkim) "Raşit ELMAS" ("Raşit Bey")